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**Crystalline Components of the Stem
Heartwood of *Randia dumatorium* and
the Roots Heartwood of *Kigelia pinnata***

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RANDIA dumatorium (Rubiaceae) is a small tree and in the indigenous system of medicine is used as a substitute for ipecacuanha (*Cephaelis ipecacuanha*). It is nauseant expectorant and diaphoretic and is considered to have anthelmintic and abortifacient properties. The fruit is said to be useful as nervine calmative and antispasmodic¹⁻². Literature revealed that some work has been reported on its stem bark³⁻⁴ and fruits⁵.

Kigelia pinnata is a small spreading tree (Bignoniaceae) with a long-stalked large gourd like fruit. The fruit is used in Africa as dressing for ulcer and for syphilis, rheumatism and as a purgative. The bark is used in rheumatism, dysentery and venereal diseases⁶. Govindachari *et al* have reported the isolation of two new dihydroisocoumarins from its roots⁷⁻⁸. The present paper describes the chemical examination of the stem heartwood of *Randia dumatorium* and the roots heartwood of *Kigelia pinnata*.

Experimental

The stem of *Randia dumatorium* and the roots of *Kigelia pinnata* used in this investigation were collected in Jaipur. A voucher specimen from this collection has been deposited in the herbarium of the Department of Botany, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur.

Microanalysis was carried out by the Australian Microanalytical Service, Division of Applied Organic Chemistry, CSIRO and University of Melbourne. Thin layer chromatographs were conducted on Merck's Kiesel gel G; in chromatographic fractionations silica gel and neutral Brockmann alumina were used and the spray reagent used in tlc was 2% ceric sulphate in 2N H₂SO₄. All melting points are uncorrected. The identity of the compounds was confirmed, unless otherwise stated, by m.m.p. co-tlc and comparison of spectra with authentic samples.

Stem Heartwood of *Randia dumatorium* : Completely dried and coarsely powdered stem heartwood (4 kg) was extracted with benzene for 3×12 hrs on steam bath. The extract was concentrated under

reduced pressure to 200 ml. The dark red benzene extract was kept in the refrigerator overnight, when a solid mass separated at the bottom. This was removed by decantation and purified by washing with benzene, when colourless crystals, subsequently identified as mannitol, were obtained. The remaining portion of the extract was chromatographed over silica gel, when the following compounds were obtained : 1. α -Amyrin-from petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) fraction, m.p. 183-84°, colourless shining needles, acetate, m.p. 222-23°; 2. β -Sitosterol-from petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 3), fraction, colourless flakes m.p. 136-37°, acetate, m.p. 126-27°, benzoate, m.p. 143°; 3. *Oleanolic acid*-from benzene-ethyl acetate (3 : 1) fraction, colourless needles, m.p. 304-5°, acetate, m.p. 266-67°; 4. *Ursolic acid*-from benzene-ethyl acetate (3 : 1) fraction, white needles, m.p. 284-85°, methyl ester, m.p. 168° and acetyl methyl ursolate, m.p. 242°; 5. *D-mannitol*-colourless crystals, m.p. 164-65°, identical with an authentic specimen, hexa-acetate m.p. 120°, phenylurethane, m.p. 301°, hexabenzate, m.p. 147-48°.

Roots Heartwood of *Kigelia pinnata* : The air dried roots (5 kg) were extracted with benzene for 12×3 hrs on water bath. The extract was concentrated under reduced pressure and was chromatographed over silica gel, when the following compounds were obtained : 1. *Octacosanol*-from petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1), m.p. 85°; acetate, m.p. 63-64°, iodide, m.p. 62-60°; 2. *Lapachol*-from petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) fraction, fine yellow needles, m.p. 139-40°; 3. β -Sitosterol-from petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 3) fraction, colourless flakes, m.p. 136-37°, acetate, m.p. 126-27°, benzoate, m.p. 143°; 4. *Kigelin*-from petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 3) fraction, colourless needles, m.p. 144°; 5. *Stigmasterol*-from benzene-ethyl acetate (3 : 1) fraction, colourless needles, m.p. 170°, acetate, m.p. 144°, benzoate, m.p. 160°; 6. *Rhodamine B*-from ethyl acetate-methanol (3 : 1) fraction, gave bright pink spot on tlc plate. On crystallization, furnished dark green crystals M⁺ C₂₈H₂₉N₂O₃. UV(MeOH) λ_{max} 260, 310, 360, 550 nm, finally confirmed by comparison with an authentic sample.

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Use of Ortho-substituted Benzalidenethiosemicarbazone in Gravimetric Determination of Palladium(II)

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DIMETHYL glyoxime and nioxime¹ have been used as analytical reagents for gravimetric determination of Pd(II). The present work with the reagents *o*-nitrobenzalidenethiosemicarbazone and *o*-chlorobenzalidenethiosemicarbazone was undertaken with a view to introduce these ligands for gravimetric determination of Ni(II), Pd(II) and Cu(II). The precipitation of Ni(II) ion is complete at pH 2-3. Thus, these ligands have an edge over the ligand dimethylglyoxime and nioxime. It has also been found that platinum does not interfere as it does not form any precipitate at pH, 2-3.

Experimental

All reagents used were of AR grade. Stock solution of Pd(II) was prepared by dissolving palladium chloride in concentrated hydrochloric acid and water. 1% solution of the ligands was employed.

Preparation of Ligands: (a) *O*-nitrobenzalidenethiosemicarbazone: It was prepared as described in the literature². (b) *O*-chlorobenzalidenethiosemicarbazone: It was prepared by dissolving *o*-chlorobenzaldehyde in ethanol and treating it with thiosemicarbazone dissolved in concentrated hydrochloric acid. The ligand was obtained as a pale yellow precipitate which was recrystallised from ethanol and dried (m.p. 217°).

Determination of Palladium: A solution containing known amount of palladium(II) was diluted to 10 ml and was heated to 50-60°. The hot solution was treated with an alcoholic solution of the ligand followed by addition of sodium acetate when brown yellow precipitate in the case of *O*-chlorobenzalidenethiosemicarbazone was obtained. The whole mass was digested on steam-bath for one

hour, filtered through a sintered glass crucible (G-4) and washed with hot water. The precipitate was dried in air over at 130-140° to constant weight, weighed as Pd(C₈H₇N₄O₂S)₂ and Pd(C₈H₇N₃SCl)₂ respectively in the case of *o*-nitrobenzalidenethiosemicarbazone and *o*-chlorobenzalidenethiosemicarbazone. The results of some of the estimations are tabulated below:

TABLE

Sl. No.	Pd(II) taken (mg)	Pd(II) found (mg)		error	
		(a)	(b)	(a)	(b)
1.	50	49.8	50.1	-0.4	+0.2
2.	40	40.1	40.1	+0.25	+0.25
3.	30	23.9	30.2	-0.33	+0.5
4.	20	20.1	19.9	+0.5	+0.5
5.	10	10.05	10.05	+0.5	+0.5

(a) With *o*-nitrobenzalidenethiosemicarbazone.
(b) With *o*-chlorobenzalidenethiosemicarbazone.

Determination of Pd(II) in the presence of other cations: Pd(II) is completely precipitated at pH=2-3 and Ni(II) is precipitated completely at pH=6-7. Thus it is easy to estimate palladium in the presence of Ni(II) and Cu(II). Pd(II) (30 mg) can be determined in the presence of 10 mg of Cu(II) and Ni(II), the maximum error being 1.5-2%.

Structure of the Chelates: *O*-substituted benzalidenethiosemicarbazones behave as bidentate ligands in neutral, ammoniacal and acid media. The chemical analysis of the complexes indicates that they have the chemical formula (I) Pd(C₈H₇N₄O₂S)₂ and (II) Pd(C₈H₇N₃SCl)₂.

The complexes are diamagnetic. Their acetone solutions show maximum absorption at about 15000 cm⁻¹. The magnetic behaviour and the electronic spectra⁴ suggest for square planar structure of the complex. The ir spectra of the complexes have been recorded to determine the nature of bonding in the complexes. The presence of a sharp band at 3050 cm⁻¹ both in ligand and the complexes indicates N-H frequency remains unchanged in the complexes. The decrease in stretching⁵⁻⁷ frequency from about 720-730 cm⁻¹ in the ligands to 630-640 cm⁻¹ in the complexes indicates M-S bonding. The presence of new bands⁸ at about 500 cm⁻¹ and 450 cm⁻¹ in the complexes indicates the coordination through N' and S. The presence of the bands at 830 cm⁻¹ indicates the presence of uncoordinated nitrite group⁹.

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